

#58 PAC: Preference-Aware Co-location Scheduling on Heterogeneous NUMA Architectures To Improve Resource Utilization

Supplementary materials for rebuttal

1 (Reviewer A+D) Comparison against Oracle

We find the optimal core allocation (Oracle) through an exhaustive search. As time is limited, we find the Oracle for eight application mixes as shown in Figure 1. Figure 1(a) shows the normalized throughput of the BE application when it is co-located with *MySQL* (high load) and *Memcached* (low load), while Figure 1(b) shows the normalized throughput of the BE application when it is co-located with *MySQL* (high load), *Xapian* (low load) and *Memcached* (low load). We observe that PAC-H averagely achieves 87.1% of the Oracle, PAC-B averagely achieves 75.9% of the Oracle and PARTIES averagely achieves 39.92% of the Oracle.

Figure 1: The normalized throughput of the BE application under different mixes of applications.

Figure 2: The normalized throughput of the BE application under different mixes of applications (2 LC and 1 BE are co-located).

Figure 3: The normalized throughput of the BE application under different mixes of applications (3 LC and 1 BE are co-located).

2 (Reviewer A) The Worst Results

Under a given application mix, we use PAC and PARTIES to schedule cores 5 times and report the average results in Section 6.2 and Section 6.3 of our paper. Figure 2 and Figure 3 show the worst results of the 5 tests. In terms of the worse case: 1) when co-locating 2 LC applications and a BE application, with PAC-H, BE applications achieve 3.96x higher throughput than with PARTIES; with PAC-B, BE applications achieve 2.61x higher throughput than with PARTIES; 2) when co-locating 3 LC applications and a BE application, with PAC-H, BE applications achieve 3.39x higher throughput than with PARTIES; with PAC-B, BE applications achieve 2.12x higher throughput than with PARTIES.

3 (Reviewer A) How PAC-H Works on Other Deployments

PAC supports UMA/homogeneous/1 LC because they are special cases of the heterogeneous NUMA architecture. For UMA/homogeneous cases, the core preference ranking of an LC application should be slightly modified:

- **UMA:** For both network-sensitive and non-network-sensitive LC applications, the brawny core is considered to have higher performance contribution than the wimpy core. Section 4 of the supplementary materials shows how PAC-H works on the UMA computer.
- **Homogeneous system:** For the network-sensitive LC application, the core with closer distance to the node which has the minimal distance to the NIC is considered to have higher performance contribution. For the non-network-sensitive LC applications, the core with closer distance to the node which stores most of the data is considered to have higher performance contribution.

For co-locating one LC application and one BE application, cores are scheduled between the two applications. We co-locate *MySQL* (high load) and *streamcluster* with PAC-H on the computer described in Table 1 of our paper. The performance of each application during scheduling is shown in Figure 4. Initially, *streamcluster* is allocated with 4 wimpy cores of Node₀ and 4 brawny cores of Node₁. *MySQL* is allocated is with 4 wimpy cores of Node₂ and 4 brawny cores of Node₃, and suffers from the QoS violation. In the next three iterations, *MySQL* uses a wimpy core to exchange a brawny core from *streamcluster* at each iteration. After that, the QoS requirement of *MySQL* is met, and the core scheduling finishes.

Figure 4: The application performance with PAC-H. The red horizontal line indicates the QoS target.

4 (Reviewer B) Evaluation on Alder Lake

Table 1: Specification

Model	Intel Core i9-12900K
Number of sockets	1
Nodes per socket	1
Cores per node	8 wimpy cores (2.4GHz), 8 brawny cores (3.2GHz)
Memory	64GB DDR4
Disk	1TB NVMe SSD
Network bandwidth	1000Mbps
Operating System	Ubuntu 22.04 (x86 Linux 5.15)

We evaluate PAC-H on an Alder Lake computer whose specification is shown in Table 1. Since the processor with Alder Lake architecture has not been adopted on server computers, we use a desktop computer with one socket as the experimental platform. Because Intel Core i9-12900K integrates heterogeneous cores in a node, the computer is UMA architecture.

We co-locate *MySQL* (high load), *Memcached* (low load) and *streamcluster*. We use PAC-H to schedule cores and show the performance of applications during the scheduling as in Figure 5. At the beginning, cores are fairly allocated to applications. Both *MySQL* and *Memcached* get 3 brawny cores and 3 wimpy cores, while *streamcluster* gets 2 brawny cores and 2 wimpy cores. *MySQL* suffers from the QoS violation. In the next two iterations, PAC-H exchanges 2 wimpy cores of *MySQL* for 2 brawny cores of *Memcached*, and the QoS violation of *MySQL* is therefore eliminated. After that, *Memcached* is still “safe” so that PAC-H exchanges a wimpy core of *streamcluster* for a brawny core of *Memcached* to improve the BE throughput. Finally, *Memcached* is not longer “safe” and the core scheduling finishes.

Figure 5: The application performance with PAC-H. The red horizontal line indicates the QoS target.

References

- [1] How to get best performance with NICs on Intel platforms https://doc.dpdk.org/guides/linux_gsg/nic_perf_intel_platform.html, 2023/4/5.
- [2] Performance Tuning. <https://docs.corundum.io/en/latest/tuning.html>, 2023/4/5.